

The semigroup $v(X)$ of upfamilies on a semilattice X

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Given a semilattice X we study the algebraic properties of the semigroup $v(X)$ of upfamilies on X . The semigroup $v(X)$ contains the Stone-Čech extension $\beta(X)$, the superextension $\lambda(X)$, and the space of filters $\varphi(X)$ on X as closed subsemigroups. We prove that $v(X)$ is a semilattice iff $\lambda(X)$ is a semilattice iff $\varphi(X)$ is a semilattice iff the semilattice X is finite and linearly ordered. We prove that the semigroup $\beta(X)$ is a band if and only if X has no infinite antichains, and the semigroup $\lambda(X)$ is commutative if and only if X is a bush with finite branches.

References

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